

TRANSLATING CULTURE SPECIFIC ITEMS IN ENGLISH LITERARY WORKS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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This article deals with the challenges of translating culture-specific items (CSIs) in English literary works and explores possible solutions to overcome them. Since such items often carry unique cultural meanings and value, their translation may lead to distortions if not handled carefully. The study highlights common strategies such as foreignization, domestication, descriptive translation, explanatory notes, aiming to preserve both meaning and cultural context.

Literary translation plays an important role in connecting cultures and making stories accessible worldwide. However, culture-specific items (CSIs) such as idioms, traditions, concepts and humor often do not have equivalents in another language which as a result pose difficulty for the translator. The translation of culture-specific items in English literary works create serious obstacles mainly because of these reasons: untranslatability, cultural loss and reader's unfamiliarity with the culture, but there are various practical solutions that can help with these challenges.

One of the main problems is that many cultural references simply do not exist in the target language. This is called untranslatability when a word or expression has no direct equivalent in target language (TL)[1]. A good example to this can be found in "Martin Eden" by Jack London where he uses the notion of "bourgeois drawing room". In this context, the term "drawing room" is difficult to translate, as it carries a specific cultural meaning which is a cultural institution rather than just a physical room which does not exist in the same way elsewhere.

Another challenge is cultural loss when a word can be translated into target language, but much of its cultural value, deep cultural meaning disappears, the translation communicates the basic meaning but fails to convey the cultural associations it has for the reader.[2] In "Martin Eden", for example the author mentions Martin and Ruth taking the ferry across San Francisco Bay. In this case, the translator can simply render this as "they took a boat", as a result the cultural connotation is lost. For the Americans this immediately evokes the 20th century West Coast culture, urban life in California and every day commuting, however, this broader meaning is lost, leaving only meaning of travelling by water.

Sometimes the difficulty comes from the fact that readers of the target text are simply unfamiliar with the culture of the original work. Reader's unfamiliarity is when even if the translation is completely accurate, the reader's understanding of the cultural item or the word may not be correct or they might not understand its significance. [3] In Martin Eden, Jack London often describes American working-class foods such as "hot cakes" or "coffee and doughnuts". For an American reader, these items immediately suggest cheap diner culture and the life condition of working-class people, laborers. However, readers from other cultures may

not share these associations and may interpret them as just ordinary food, without the social and cultural meaning they carry in the original text.

Despite these challenges, there are some strategies that can help with the translation of CSIs. First and probably the most widely known one is foreignization where the original term is kept in the source language, even if it feels "foreign" to the reader.[4] The goal is to preserve cultural authenticity and let the reader experience the text as something tied to its original culture. For instance, keeping *Oakland ferry* (Martin Eden) as it is in English rather than translating it as just "a boat" preserves the Californian setting and historical reality and give the reader cultural weight and an American vibe.

Domestication is another strategy that is used in translation. Here the translator adapts the culture-specific item into something more familiar for the target audience, the expression or the phrase is domesticated, making it more understandable and comfortable for the reader.[5] For instance, "hot cakes" can be translated as "pancakes", since it is a closer equivalent and familiar to most readers. Some nuance is lost, but the text remains close to original word and clear. The last two solutions are the descriptive translation where the word is not translated word-for-word but the cultural meaning is delivered with description in a target language(it works best when there's no direct equivalent in the TL and when cultural context would otherwise be lost) and the another one is providing explanatory notes where extra information is added, either as a footnote, endnote, or bracketed comment to help the reader understand the cultural background.[6] It is particularly effective for literary works where preserving meaning is more important than smooth flow.

To conclude, it is true that there some culture specific items that create challenges when translating, as their cultural deep meaning may disappear. However, by applying appropriate strategies such as foreignization, domestication, descriptive translation, or using explanatory notes can help us minimize their losses and deliver it to reader as relatively close to the original text and let them grasp the richness of it. Although perfect equivalence is rarely possible, careful choice of strategy allows literature to reach readers worldwide, carrying not only the words but the spirit of the culture as well.

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